

MDMC

Master in Data Management
and Curation

MASTER IN DATA MANAGEMENT AND
CURATION

**Extending NOMAD schemas for
the UMIL NFFA-DI Theory &
Simulation Installation, with a
focus on the Yambo code**

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- [PRP@CERIC : Pathogen Readiness Platform for Ceric - Eric Upgrade](#)

Author's Declaration

I, ELENA MOLteni, declare that this thesis entitled, 'EXTENDING NOMAD SCHEMAS FOR THE UMIL NFFA-DI THEORY & SIMULATION INSTALLATION, WITH A FOCUS ON THE YAMBO CODE' and the work presented therein are my own.

I certify that:

- This work was performed wholly or principally during MDMC internship in the UMIL THEO&SIM LAB.
- If any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have relied on the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
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- With respect to AI technologies:
 - No content generated by AI technologies was presented as my own work.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always cited. Except for such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all major sources of help.

Signed:

Date: 29-04-2025

“Data! Data! Data!... I cannot make bricks without clay.”

Sherlock Holmes in “The adventure of the copper beeches”, A. Conan Doyle

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Abstract

This thesis describes the work I have performed at the UMIL Operative Unit (OU) of the NFFA-DI project, as the "internship" part of the Master in Data Management and Curation, after the in-presence learning part. In this context, I have undertaken several tasks related to data management and curation for the computational part (UMIL Theo&Sim lab) of the NFFA-DI UMIL OU. In the UMIL Theo&Sim lab we perform computational material science research: the main focus is on Density Functional Theory characterization of the structural, electronic, magnetic and optical properties of bulk crystals, surfaces, interfaces, adsorbates; some research is also done on classical molecular dynamics modeling of friction.

These are the main lines along which my data management and curation activity has been developed:

- NOMAD is the platform chosen by NFFA-DI for the storage of computational material science research data and metadata according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. I have identified and addressed some extension opportunities in the NOMAD parsers for some of the simulation codes used in our OU

- I have organized NOMAD hands-on meetings for training OU colleagues on the use of NOMAD for the upload of computational material science data

- I have installed an Oasis (i.e. a local instance of NOMAD) on my computer, and contacted and assisted the IT team of our Department in installing an Oasis to be used by the whole UMIL OU

- I have prepared the Data Management Plans and Interactive Remote Access forms for all the computational techniques offered by the UMIL Theo&Sim lab to external users through user calls

Contents

1	Introduction and Motivation	7
1.1	The importance of data	7
1.2	Open Science and FAIR data	10
1.2.1	Open Science	10
1.2.2	FAIR data	12
1.3	FAIR principles for computational material science: state of the art	14
2	Our project	17
2.1	The NFFA-DI project	17
2.2	The UMIL Theory&Simulation lab	18
2.3	NOMAD and our codes	20
3	Strategy	27
3.1	Overview of NOMAD functionalities and possible extensions for our codes	27
3.1.1	Extension opportunities	28
3.2	Objectives	28
4	Results	30
4.1	Data Management Plans and Interactive Remote Access forms	30
4.2	NOMAD Oasis	34
4.3	QE band structure plotting	35
4.4	Yambo GW calculations	41
4.5	Yambo cell parameters	44
4.6	Yambo spectra	50
4.7	Siesta	52
5	Conclusions and perspectives	56

Chapter 1

Introduction and Motivation

1.1 The importance of data

Scientific research has nothing to do with solving complex and intricate crime cases. Nevertheless, what these two unrelated activities have in common, in order to be conducted in a meaningful and fruitful way, is the need for data. So, similarly to Sherlock Holmes complaining about not having enough data available on which to build his deductions, any scientist, either an experimentalist, a computational researcher or a theoretician, will not be able to make good science - or science at all - if they have no data (either their own, or taken from the scientific literature) to build upon, that is, either to interpret, or to use in order to verify some hypothesis, or to build new hypotheses or models.

Depending on the specific scientific discipline, data can be the result of laboratory measurements, or of observations, of simulations, of clinical trials, and so on. However, even the most abstract theory or model can be recognized by the scientific community as interesting and worthy of consideration only insofar as it is expected to be somehow - possibly in the future thanks to novel, currently not yet developed, technologies - liable of being tested against some data.

In the past century and in the current one, the amount of data available, in particular for some scientific disciplines, has increased enormously: particle physics and genome research are impressive examples. Accordingly, expressions like "big data", or "data mining", have become popular. Scientists, especially in some research fields, have moved from a situation where they "did not have enough data" to one where they had to find efficient ways to store and manage the large amount of data new techniques or instruments enabled them to obtain, and to extract the maximal possible useful informa-

tion from these data. Even outside the scientific domain, the importance of relying on data - and on the ability to efficiently handle, store, organize them and extract all the possible information from them - has become more and more explicitly recognized, so that now we hear and read about data-driven management, marketing, decision making etc.

Both in science and in other areas of life, if we have to rely on data, these data need to be *...reliable*, precisely. Relying on bad quality data is worse than having no data at all (or not enough data), as much as being misled is worse than being aware of our ignorance (or limited knowledge). With the advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the need for *good quality data* has become crucial. Indeed, there is a qualitative - not quantitative - difference in the way in which Machine Learning (ML) [1, 2, 3] vs. "standard" scientific research (and scientific coding) use data. ML is *intrinsically* data-driven, possibly in the same way as Quantum Mechanics is *intrinsically* probabilistic.

As illustrated in Figure 1.1, in traditional coding (top panel) the code contains a set of instructions, in a given programming language, to perform a series of operations on some input data, thus producing some outputs. The instructions correspond to "rules", which in scientific programming are indeed the "rules" which the investigated system obeys according to the currently accepted models, e.g. the newtonian equations of motion for classical molecular dynamics codes, or the Schroedinger equation (or derived equations or approximated models) in ab initio codes. Already in this case the quality and reliability of the used input data is important, of course. But, importantly, the code contains "the physics of the system", or at least an approximated model of it. This is precisely the reason why sometimes simulations are referred to as "*in silico* experiments": we can safely assume that, if the code has no errors and the used model contains all the interactions, parameters etc. which are relevant for describing the behaviour of the investigated system, then the results we will obtain by running our simulation will be in agreement with those we would obtain by performing the corresponding experimental measurement on that system.

On the other hand, in Machine Learning, first there is a training phase (Fig. 1.1, center panel), where the machine learning algorithm is "fed" with very large amounts of data, both of the types we normally consider as inputs and outputs of an experiment or simulation - for instance, in material science the inputs may be the chemical compositions of possible materials and the outputs their crystal structures, or the inputs may be the crystal structures and the outputs their electronic band structures or optical absorption spectra - and the "rules" connecting the inputs and the outputs are "learned" from the data.

Then (bottom panel) new input data (different from those used in the

Figure 1.1: Comparison of the traditional programming approach and ML. Top: Traditional programming approach, where the computer is supplied with input data and an explicitly specified extensive list of rules. Center and bottom: ML approach: Center: training phase: the computer is supplied with prepared examples of inputs and outputs (training data) and rules are learned from the data; Bottom: model prediction: new input data is fed into the ML model that contains already learned rules. Results are predicted values, in this case, the forecast of the Vertical Total Electron Content in the ionosphere (from [4]).

training phase) are given in input to the ML code, which will now use the learned rules to obtain the output results from the given inputs.

The crucial issue here is that, at a difference with traditional coding, the

ML algorithm developer will in general *not* code any of the "physics of the system", i.e. models, equations etc describing that class of systems according to the state of the art in a specific scientific discipline, in the ML algorithm, but they will let the algorithm find them by itself, so to say - although sometimes constraints based on scientific knowledge can be included, as a help to the algorithm, restricting the configuration space it can explore by excluding solutions which are known to be impossible.

The fact that the quality of Machine Learning results heavily relies on both the amount and the quality of the used training data is by now firmly established. Indeed, since the ML algorithm has to find out the "rules" based on its training data, if the training data are wrong, or possibly not wrong but biased or incomplete to describe a given class of systems, then the ML algorithm will learn wrong or biased or incomplete rules, and then apply them to the "real" input data, obtaining wrong or biased or incomplete results.

Also in traditional scientific coding we can obtain unreliable scientific results, if we use a wrong or incomplete model to describe our investigated system, but in that case the model is clearly defined and debugging is relatively straightforward. On the other hand, as it was once said that in semiconductor heterostructures "the interface is the device"[5], in Machine Learning we may say that "the data is the model" (meaning that we have not coded any physical model or rules, and the rules have to be learned from the training data). All this discussion highlights the importance of the availability of large amounts of *high quality* - i.e. reliable - data for the ever increasing field of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence tools.

1.2 Open Science and FAIR data

1.2.1 Open Science

Open Science is a set of values, principles, and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone, for the benefit of the whole humanity (see e.g. [6] and refs. therein). It entails not only open access to the products of scientific research, but also participation in the process of knowledge production (e.g. through practices such as citizen science and crowdsourcing).

According to the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2011) [7, 8], six Guiding Principles of Open Science can be defined, which I will hereafter list and briefly review:

- 1) Transparency: more transparency in both the outcomes of scientific

research and the processes, methods etc used to obtain them allows both validation of results and their reliable extension to further systems. Needless to say, transparency is also an antidote to several forms of scientific misconduct: the higher is the amount of details on the experimental or computational or observational setup which is made available, the less room is left for the fabrication or falsification of data: this benefits the whole scientific community and increases public trust in science.

2) Equality of opportunities: everyone should have the possibility to access to scientific knowledge, benefit from this knowledge and its applications, and also contribute to the process of generating it

3) Responsibility, respect and accountability: this principle involves intellectual integrity and the respect of ethical principles in the conduct of scientific research

4) Collaboration, participation and inclusion: this is probably the first idea, together with Principle 1, transparency, that comes to our mind intuitively when we hear the expression "Open Science". Open Science aims at encouraging collaboration, both among scientists, either within the same or different disciplines, and also between scientists and non-scientists

5) Flexibility: this expresses the view (based on experience) that there is no "one-size-fits-all" way of conducting Open Science, since every scientific discipline and every local and institutional context has its own practices, challenges and opportunities

6) Sustainability: Open Science should be built on long-term, sustainable practices, services, and funding models.

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science has also defined four pillars of Open Science, which help in "translating" the above-mentioned Principles into practical policies:

- 1) Open scientific knowledge
- 2) Open science infrastructure
- 3) Open engagement of societal actors
- 4) Open dialogue with other knowledge systems

I will comment here on Pillars 1 and 2, which are the most relevant ones for my present work. In particular, Pillar 1 includes open scientific publications, open research data and metadata, open source software, open hardware, open educational resources (OER). The adjective "open" means here "in the public domain or under copyright and licensed under an open license that allows access, re-use, repurpose, adaptation and distribution under specific conditions (e.g., attribution)", such as Creative Commons (cc) licenses, typically in their "cc by" form. Pillar 2 instead considers as science

infrastructures both the "physical" ones, i.e. experimental instruments, laboratories and facilities, and the "virtual" ones, i.e. computational facilities.

The potential benefits of Open Science to the research community and to society are manifold, ranging from a more efficient use of resources and a faster progress of science and consequent technological developments (obtained by avoiding unnecessary duplication of research and minimizing the cases of research misconduct and related unreliable research results, through openly accessible research results and methods), more transparency as to the methods and results of research, leading to an increased trust of the general public towards science, which can in turn facilitate science-informed decision making, and increased opportunities of collaboration and interdisciplinary research.

1.2.2 FAIR data

The FAIR principles (see e.g. [9]) were introduced to help make research data more open and easy to re-use, and thereby promote Open Science. The by now well-known FAIR acronym stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.

"Findable" means easy to be found both by human beings and by machines. The many references to "machine -findable" or "-accessible" or "-actionable" we are going to find from now on in this discussion are aimed at both the possibility of automated data retrieval and the use of data as "training datasets" for AI models. We have already discussed the need of Machine Learning and more in general AI models for high quality data, and the findability and accessibility - also by machines - of research data that are endowed with rich metadata describing their provenance, experimental or computational or observational details etc is crucial for being able to assess their quality. Findability can be achieved through the use of rich metadata and of globally unique and persistent identifiers, such as a DOI (Digital Object Identifier). Moreover, data, or at least their metadata, should also be stored or indexed in a searchable resource. Metadata are "data about data": they can be of various types: administrative (e.g. who is the author of the data, licenses etc.), structural (in online structured data repositories for scientific data: type of variable [integer, float, ..], its units), descriptive metadata about the experiment or simulation (experimental conditions or simulation parameters).

"Accessible" means that data and metadata are retrievable (both by humans and machines) using a standardized communication protocol which should allow for authentication and authorization procedures, where necessary. Moreover, metadata must be accessible even when data are no longer

available. It is important to stress that accessible does not automatically mean "totally open". There can be cases when data cannot be openly shared, e.g. due to personal data protection, intellectual property issues etc. The general guiding principle can therefore be summarized as "As open as possible, as close as necessary". However, what must always be open is the metadata.

"Interoperability" is here intended in regard to research data, but it can have a broader meaning, encompassing also scientific instruments which are used to obtain such data. Interoperability of devices or data means that they can be integrated with each other and work seamlessly together. This requires compatibility of devices or of datasets, and relies on the existence or creation of standards, plus in some cases the use of "converters". Standards can be either "physical" (the exact shape of a plug, specific voltage or current values, etc) or "virtual" such as having the same data formats for two different simulation codes. "Converters" instead are either physical devices or softwares which allow the "translation" from one "format" - either of devices or of data - to another (e.g. adapters for electrical and electronic devices, format converters for data). To build converters one needs to know both languages, we may say, remaining in the metaphor of language translation, but in fact this entails (implicitly in the case of human languages) understanding the structure of languages at a more abstract level.

Here vocabularies and ontologies come into play: a *Vocabulary* is the set of terms and their definitions used to describe concepts within a particular domain, while an *Ontology* is a formal representation of knowledge in a given domain, i.e. a formal description of a set of concepts and their relationships. A vocabulary can be built also without an ontology, but the existence of an underlying ontology will make the vocabulary more robust and standardized. To be interoperable, research data should use *vocabularies* built with standardized terms and definitions that are widely recognized and accepted within the relevant community. In addition, data and metadata need to be machine-readable and machine-actionable. This discussion shows that, out of the four principles composing the acronym FAIR, the I, i.e. Interoperability, is often the most challenging one.

Finally, in order to be "Reusable" - which is indeed the real aim of the whole FAIR paradigm, and also of Open Science (research data being usable by other researchers, possibly also from different scientific disciplines, enhancing thus the advancement of science) - data and metadata need to be richly described, following domain-relevant standards, associated with a detailed provenance and released with a clear and accessible data usage license specifying who can use the data and to which purposes.

1.3 FAIR principles for computational material science: state of the art

Computational material science is one of the scientific fields where the need and advantage of obtaining data for a large variety of systems has become evident to researchers in recent decades. Somehow following a similar path to the one of genomic research, also in material science the concept of high-throughput calculations has gained importance. Of course, also in this case, finding ways to easily and rapidly perform e.g. electronic structure calculations on large numbers of different materials is only the beginning. Then one has to find easy and efficient ways to extract relevant scientific information from these data.

Also in this particular case, as already discussed at a general level in the previous sections, the extraction of relevant information from scientific data relies on the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of such data, namely on the FAIR principles.

Regarding the already mentioned need of good quality data for use in Machine Learning techniques, recent reviews[10], analyzing the type of data (computational, experimental) used as training data for ML models in materials science, have found a considerable relative weight of computational data in general, with a predominance of DFT-generated data. The authors also observe a more advanced stage of development - so far - of common databases and tools for performing ML in materials science based on simulation data with respect to the situation for data from other domains of materials science (e.g. synthesis and experimental characterization). They relate this to the complexity and heterogeneity of experimental data, making data cleaning and standardization challenging. Seen from this point of view, the current predominance of DFT-generated data as training sets for Machine Learning in materials research may ensure good data quality – within the range of applicability of DFT. Of course a future enhanced standardization of data from several experimental domains in materials science is desirable, and it may lead to a larger use of such experimental data as training sets for ML models.

We have already mentioned that Interoperability is often the most challenging of the four principles defining "FAIR", and computational material science is no exception in this respect. In this field, there are families of codes performing to a large extent the same types of calculations, and most of the time assigning different names and possibly using different units for variables representing the same physical quantities, or different formats for the same "objects" (e.g. atomic coordinates, k-point grids, ...). Even in the

case of pairs of codes whose developer communities actively collaborate - where for instance one of the two codes is explicitly expected to read some output of the other one - the best that developers can think of is writing format converters: an example is the joint use of the QuantumEspresso and Yambo codes. Finally, it often happens, even within a single code, that a new version of the code requires different input formats with respect to previous versions.

Open data repositories for material science are a precious resource towards interoperability and reusability in this field of research, in particular if they store data in a structured way, with rich metadata and a common vocabulary.

Several projects, tools and repositories exist in material science, aiming at high-throughput simulations and/or acting as structured data repositories. As examples, we can mention:

- the MaX project (MAterials design at the eXascale, <https://www.max-centre.eu/>) is a European Center of Excellence which enables materials modelling, simulations, discovery and design at the frontiers of High Performance Computing (HPC), High Throughput Computing (HTC) and data analytics technologies. It works along several different lines, from providing open source material science codes, also porting and optimizing them for peta- and exascale platforms, to data curation according to the FAIR principles. It offers an ecosystem for automated high-throughput calculations and the automatic storage of data in graph databases which is based on AiiDA (<https://www.aiida.net/>) as the working environment and on the Materials Cloud (<https://www.materialscloud.org/home>) as the cloud simulation and web dissemination and sharing platform.

- the Materials Genome Initiative (<https://www.mgi.gov/>), a US federal multi-agency initiative for discovering, manufacturing, and deploying advanced materials in a fast and cost-effective way, by investing in the R&D infrastructure needed to accelerate the discovery and development process, e.g. in artificial intelligence-powered autonomous experimentation (AI/AE) relevant to sustainable semiconductor manufacturing, and in Machine Learning models for materials properties prediction.

- the Materials Project (<https://next-gen.materialsproject.org/>), which provides both access to computational results on known and predicted materials, by enabling queries across a variety of properties and types of systems (synthesis recipes, batteries, catalysts, and molecules) through the Materials Explorer, and analysis tools through web apps.

- the NOMAD data repository (<https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/>), developed and maintained by the FAIRmat consortium (<https://www.fairmat-nfdi.eu/fairmat/>). NOMAD provides tools for material science data management, sharing, publishing, exploring and analyzing; it aims at Interoperabil-

ity by converting data from a variety of simulation codes to a unified format and organizing the data on materials properties in a common structure of classes and subclasses, allowing easy querying by the use of a variety of filters (chemical composition, type of computed physical property, used simulation code, author, etc.). NOMAD was chosen by the NFFA-DI project as the data repository for its research data, as will be illustrated more in detail in the next Chapter.

Chapter 2

Our project

2.1 The NFFA-DI project

The NFFA-DI (Nano Foundries and Fine Analysis - Digital Infrastructure, nffa-di.it) project [11] is funded under the italian PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan), in the category of Research Infrastructures upgrade. It builds upon the activity and experience of the previous - and still active - european NFFA network (<https://nffa.eu/>). The NFFA-DI project aims at building an italian distributed Research Infrastructure (RI) for nanoscience and nanotechnology, bridging the gap between fundamental research and functional micro- systems for the digital transformation.

The project envisages the digital access to a wide portfolio of services through the setup of a Single Entry Point (SEP) and a catalogue of advanced experimental and computational resources, and the FAIR-by-design management of research data.

The distributed RI will integrate facilities for atomically controlled growth, structural characterization of nano-objects and nanostructured materials, experimental facilities for the fine analysis of matter using synchrotron radiation (at Elettra), and upscaling of the most promising systems to the level of intermediate TRL developments.

This will be achieved by the upgrading of the laboratories at the various NFFA-DI Operative Units (OU) through the purchase and/or updating of experimental instrumentation, and by the implementation and use of specific open source softwares and open platforms for the FAIR-by-design handling of research data.

Four institutions participate in the NFFA-DI project (<https://nffa-di.it/en/about-us/consortium/>): the italian Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), Area Science Park, Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI) and

Università degli Studi di Milano (UMIL), resulting in a total of 11 Operative Units (CNR participates with 8 OUs).

The available experimental and computational techniques are organized into five "Installations" (<https://nffa-di.it/en/our-offer/>):

- Lithography & Patterning
- Growth & Synthesis
- Advanced Characterization and Fine Analysis
- Theory & Simulation
- Upscale to intermediate TRL

This wide spectrum of experimental instruments and techniques and computational methods and softwares will be made available to academic and industrial researchers through the submission and evaluation of research proposals (through the Single Entry Point) during periodic user calls. A first call has already been concluded and the second one is going to close on April 30th 2025.

2.2 The UMIL Theory&Simulation lab

The NFFA-DI UMIL Operative Unit, at the Physics Department (<https://fisica.unimi.it/en/home>) of Università degli Studi di Milano, consists of both an experimental and a computational lab. My work for the present Master course - to which I am participating as "staff participant" from the UMIL OU where I currently work within a fixed term Technologist position funded by NFFA-DI - is focused on data management and curation activities for the computational lab (part of the NFFA-DI Theory & Simulation Installation) of the UMIL OU, henceforth "UMIL Theo&Sim lab". Before my current NFFA-DI technologist position, I have been performing research activity in computational materials science (specifically, Density Functional Theory studies on surfaces, molecules and adsorbates) in the same research group for some years, so that I am familiar with at least some of the computational methods and codes used in the UMIL Theo&Sim lab.

The mentioned data management and curation activities include both the alignment of the OU data management to the NFFA-DI general data policies through the setup of Data Management Plans (DMPs) and Interactive Remote Access (IRA) forms, and the work on extending some NOMAD parsers for electronic structure codes in order to adapt them to needs of our OU. NOMAD general features and its role in NFFA-DI data management will be discussed in Section 2.3 of this Chapter, while the general structure of DMPs and IRA forms within the NFFA-DI project and their specificities for our OU will be described in Chapter 4.

In the UMIL Theo&Sim lab, several different codes and computational methods are both used internally and offered to external users within the periodic NFFA-DI calls for user projects. Within the catalog (<https://nffa-di.it/en/our-offer/>) on the NFFA-DI Single Entry Point (SEP), the computational techniques offered by the UMIL Theo&Sim lab are classified as follows:

* Structural and Ground State Electronic Properties (SGSEP): this technique groups electronic structure computational methods and codes for determining the electronic and geometric ground state of crystals, surfaces, molecules and for investigating its properties, ranging from equilibrium geometry to electronic band structures to phonon dispersion. The codes available within UMIL Theo&Sim for this technique are QuantumEspresso (QE: <https://www.quantum-espresso.org/> [12, 13]) and Siesta (<https://siesta-project.org/siesta/> [14, 15]). Both are open source codes. QE is a plane wave (PW) DFT code especially tailored for the simulation of crystals, i.e. periodic systems: bulk systems, surfaces, interfaces, 2D materials (although it can be used also for isolated systems such as molecules). Siesta, on the other hand, uses a basis of localized atomic orbitals, thus allowing the handling of surfaces, interfaces, 3D and 2D materials also with large periodicity (up to thousands of atoms) due to reconstructions, moiré patterns, matching of crystal structures: relevant examples of applications are: defects in 2D and 3D crystals, organic-inorganic hybrid interfaces, heterostructures

* Magnetic Properties (MP): this technique includes electronic structure computational methods and codes used to simulate both ground-state properties of magnetic systems and spin-orbit related properties. Also for this technique, the codes available within UMIL Theo&Sim are QuantumEspresso and Siesta. Both codes can be used to perform spin-polarized calculations for bulk magnetic materials, surfaces and interfaces - in the case of Siesta also including up to thousands of atoms. Examples of application are ultra-thin surface oxides and spinterfaces formed by a magnetic substrate and an organic molecular layer.

* Excited State Properties (ESP): this technique relates to the simulation of the excited state properties of complex and realistic systems, e.g. bulk systems, surfaces, molecules, nanostructured materials, and combinations of them, using many-body perturbation theory (MBPT). The code available within UMIL Theo&Sim for this technique is Yambo[16], also an open source code (Website: <https://www.yambo-code.eu>, Github: <https://github.com/yambo-code/yambo>). It allows the evaluation of quasi-particle band structures, optical absorption spectra, electron energy loss spectra (EELS), Kerr effect, circular dichroism (CD), excitonic effects, electron-

phonon interaction, real-time propagation.

* Transport Properties (TP): this technique involves the calculation of electronic quantum charge transport through junctions at the nanoscale, molecular contacts, 1D and 2D systems, bulk heterostructures. It includes Green's function Landauer formalism and Wannier functions-based implementation for efficient transport calculations on realistically complex quantum contacts and functionalized systems. It also allows the calculation of spin-dependent conductivities for spintronics applications. The code available within UMIL Theo&Sim for this technique is TranSiesta (<https://www.simuneatomistics.com/siesta-toolkit/siesta-code/>). Examples of applications are graphene-based nanojunctions and molecular nanojunctions.

* Atoms and Molecules in Motion (AMM): this technique can in principle include all the models and codes which allow the simulation of dynamical processes in materials, ranging from Ab initio Molecular Dynamics (AIMD) to Atomistic and also Coarse-Grained Force Field (FF) Molecular Dynamics. Currently the available code within UMIL Theo&Sim for this technique is LAMMPS. LAMMPS (<https://www.lammps.org/#gsc.tab=0> [17]) is a well-established open source simulation platform for the modeling of the structural and dynamical properties of polymeric, biological, solid-state (metals, ceramics, oxides), granular, or even coarse-grained macroscopic systems. It uses a variety of interatomic potentials (force fields, including machine-learned ones, developed by the group) and boundary conditions. It allows to simulate large systems up to millions or even billions of atoms. It can be used to study nanotribology, nano-assembled systems, complex organic/inorganic interfaces in various conditions.

2.3 NOMAD and our codes

NOMAD is the Data Repository chosen by the NFFA-DI project for the upload, storage and publishing of its research data in a structured way according to the FAIR principles (see NFFA-DI Deliverable D1.2).

NOMAD [18] is a free and open source web-based repository, developed by the German FAIRmat consortium, for FAIR Research Data Management in materials science (both computational and experimental). NOMAD allows the setup of local Oasis, i.e. local instances of NOMAD, with the same functionalities as the "global" NOMAD platform. This enables users to implement new functionalities, tailored to their specific needs (e.g. simulation codes or specific experimental techniques or instrument types which are not yet supported by the NOMAD platform), on their project or institution Oasis, ensuring local research data management according to the FAIR prin-

principles, with the possibility of preparing these data for the subsequent upload and publishing on the general NOMAD platform (Fig. 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of the data flow from local devices to a local Oasis to the general NOMAD platform (image from NOMAD Tutorial 8 part 1 and other NOMAD tutorials and materials).

The NFFA-DI project has set up a project Oasis on its OFED (Overarching Fair Ecosystem for Data) datalake (Fig. 2.2), which is hosted on the ORFEO Data Center of the Area Science Park NFFA-DI OU. The flow of research data from the various NFFA-DI Operative Units to the OFED datalake is structured in three levels:

- OU level: raw data are generated by scientific instruments or by simulation codes in the lab, enriched with metadata and stored on the local servers.
- Datalake level: data from the OUs are validated and sent to the OFED datalake, with appropriate data security protocols. Data are verified and, if necessary, standardized according to the FAIR principles. The resulting processed data and metadata are stored on the NFFA-DI Oasis
- Data repository level: the final data and metadata are published on the NOMAD data repository, being thus endowed with Persistent Identifiers and no longer modifiable. Scientific publications and other documents will

instead be published on Zenodo or other equivalent platform, also assigning them a PID.

Figure 2.2: Scheme of the data flow from the NFFA-DI OUs to the OFED datalake (from Fig. 1 of NFFA-DI deliverable D1.2).

A key concept in NOMAD (as in good - and in particular FAIR - Research Data Management in general) is that of *structured data*. Of course having our research data securely stored in an openly accessible platform is already a step forward with respect to not having shared them (or the part which can be shared) at all. However, the added value of repositories like NOMAD is the possibility of storing and showing structured data, accompanied by metadata.

Structuring means that uploaded raw research data and metadata, possibly in several different formats and coming from several different sources such as - considering the most general case - digital outputs of measurement instruments, contents of Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs), input and output files of simulation softwares or of data analysis tools, are processed, so to be converted and stored into standardized formats, using standardized vocabularies and organizing them into a hierarchical structure consisting of sections and subsections. This allows the integration of different types of data about the same physical system into a unique "object" (named an *archive* in NOMAD), and a user-friendly querying of these data (Fig. 2.3). The same

workflow holds both when uploading data to the general NOMAD platform or to a local Oasis.

Figure 2.3: Schematic representation of the data flow in NOMAD, for different types of data (from NOMAD Tutorial 8 part 1 and other NOMAD tutorials and materials).

In NOMAD this is achieved by using standardized Data Models (NOMAD Data Models, Sections etc. are described and documented in a rich collection of tutorials <https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/tutorials.html> and documentation pages <https://nomad-lab.eu/prod/v1/docs/>). To build a Data Model, first a Data Schema has to be defined, i.e. a formal description of data, data types, and data file structure. Then a Template has to be created, i.e. an instance of the Data Schema, and finally the template has to be filled with "real" data, thus obtaining a structured archive file.

The NOMAD code is written in Python and consists of a general part and specific parts for each of the NOMAD-supported simulation codes (and experimental techniques). Restricting ourselves to the case of computational data, the general part of NOMAD contains tools for performing operations which are common to the processing of data from any kind of simulation code, for instance tools for parsing several types of file formats (like text, xml, hdf5), for writing or plotting physical quantities, and the definitions of Base Sections. The simulation code-specific parts instead contain the parsers for each of the NOMAD-supported codes, which are divided into electronic

structure codes and "atomistic" codes.

This classification, distinguishing electronic vs. atomistic, is probably a result of the historical development of NOMAD and it should in principle reflect the distinction between *ab initio* vs. classical Molecular Dynamics (MD) codes, but in fact this distinction is not so clear-cut. First, there can be codes which can perform both *ab initio* and classical simulations, and in these cases the assignment to either of the two groups will be rather arbitrary: the CHARMM software, for instance, mainly known as a classical MD code, but also supporting multi-scale techniques as QM/MM, is grouped in NOMAD under "electronic-parsers". Moreover, some quantities are common to codes which are currently classified into the two different existing groups. As a first example we can mention quantities related to series of values of a given physical quantity (e.g. the total energy) as a function of the simulation step number: these quantities are common to *ab initio* MD, classical MD, and *ab initio* and classical geometry optimization. As a second example we can mention quantities such as cell size, atom type, coordinates, which are in principle common to all the considered codes of the two groups, i.e. both the *ab initio* and the classical ones, and for any kind of calculation (ground state properties, spectra, geometry optimization...). On the other hand, there can be codes belonging to the same group, e.g. the electronic-parsers one, which perform rather different types of calculations, such as ground state electronic structure vs. geometry optimization or *ab initio* MD vs. excited state properties, although based on the same computational framework (DFT and beyond-DFT methods). Such different types of calculations involve the presence or absence of specific physical quantities, like trajectories as mentioned above, band structures, spectra. Based on this discussion, we can conclude that such a strict separation of codes in these two distinct "electronic" and "atomistic" categories, and more in general the enforcement of strict taxonomies when designing data schemas, are not particularly helpful, and indeed the separation between electronic-parsers and atomistic-parsers will probably be deprecated soon. More abstract and polymorphic models may instead help make NOMAD more flexible and adaptable both to the future support for further simulation codes and for the possible implementation of new functionalities and calculated physical quantities in future versions of already NOMAD-supported codes, thus contributing to NOMAD's long-term sustainability.

Going back to the description of the NOMAD structure, specific Sections, adapted to the needs of the various types of simulation or experimental techniques, are built, starting from the Base Sections and taking advantage of Python "inheritance" and "composition". This results in a hierarchical organization in sections and subsections, and a "modular" structure of the whole

NOMAD code, which in turn make the NOMAD entries more easily readable and searchable, and the coding of additional features easier for the FAIRmat team or external contributing users.

Figure 2.4: Scheme of NOMAD base sections (from FAIRmat Tutorial 14, Part 2 - NOMAD-Simulations)

In order to illustrate the hierarchical organization of NOMAD into sections and subsections, which holds both for experimental and computational data and metadata, we can comment Figure 2.4. As shown in the Figure, we can have a very general Abstract Base Section "Activity", containing several still rather general types of activity, i.e. Process (which in NOMAD refers to the growth of materials), Measurement (several experimental characterization techniques), BaseSimulation (for simulation data). Then, as a further level, we can have standard NOMAD plugins for Base Sections describing specific types e.g. of growth or characterization techniques, but still not for a specific instrument: e.g. PhysicalVaporDeposition under Process, or PowderDiffraction under Measurement. Finally, there are User Schemas, which are lab-, instrument- or simulation code-specific and contain custom sections, created by users applying one or more Base Sections. Restricting ourselves to the case of simulation data, the Simulation section is composed of four main subsections:

- * Program, which contains all the metadata about the used simulation software (program name, version, ..)

- * ModelSystem, which contains all the metadata about the investigated system, such as atom positions, simulation cell, symmetries

- * ModelMethod, containing the methodological metadata, divided into two groups: one regarding the mathematical model or approximation used (e.g. DFT, GW, ForceFields) and the other describing the used numerical settings (type of meshes, self-consistent parameters, basis sets settings, ...)

- * Outputs, containing all the properties obtained as outputs of a given simulation.

It should be mentioned that the above-discussed Figure 2.4 describes the new plugin-based NOMAD schema, which is under development. The majority of NOMAD's computational parsers do not yet exist as plugins, but they are instead linked to the nomad-lab software as submodules. The current schema is based on a "Run" section in the archive, with the subsections Program (with Quantities such as program name, version etc.), Method (with subsections for the type of xc functional used in DFT, k-point mesh etc.), System (with Quantities such as the chemical formula, and subsections for e.g. atom coordinates, crystal symmetries), Calculation (with subsections for calculated properties, like energy, forces, band gap, eigenvalues..). However, the general hierarchical and modular concept of having sections and subsections, using python inheritance, is followed in both the "old" and the "new" implementation.

Several simulation codes among those mostly used in the UMIL Theo&Sim lab are included in the list of NOMAD-supported codes on the general NOMAD website, in particular QuantumEspresso (QE), Yambo, Siesta, LAMMPS. This means that there exist specific parsers for these codes. However, a first very simple test upload of Yambo data showed us that NOMAD is somehow missing several types of data and metadata from Yambo calculations, resulting in an Overview page with little relevant scientific information on the studied systems. In particular, in the Material section within the Overview page, information on the chemical formula and on the cell type and size is missing, and spectra, which are generally the main scientific output of Yambo runs, are not plotted. We have therefore decided to investigate these issues more in detail and to select specific features to be implemented in the NOMAD parsers, within my MDMC internship work, together with further data management tasks, namely the writing of the Data Management Plans and Interactive Remote Access forms for the computational techniques offered by UMIL Theo&Sim.

Chapter 3

Strategy

3.1 Overview of NOMAD functionalities and possible extensions for our codes

The preliminary observations made in section 2.3 point to the fact that, even for those codes which are NOMAD-supported, some extension opportunities can still be identified in order to expand the range of data and metadata that can be extracted and displayed by NOMAD. I decided therefore to investigate more in detail the degree of completeness in the data and metadata extracted and reported by NOMAD for the codes of interest for the UMIL Theo&Sim lab.

To this aim, I have organized hands-on sessions on the use of NOMAD for each of the chosen codes, each with the participation of the UMIL Theo&Sim colleagues using the specific code chosen. The aim of these hands-on sessions was twofold:

- 1) explaining the use of NOMAD to those colleagues who had no previous experience with it: indeed dissemination of the knowledge acquired during the Master in-presence lessons is also explicitly foreseen among the activities to be carried out by MDMC students during their internship at the NFFA-DI OUs,

- 2) identifying NOMAD extension opportunities, among which we may choose the ones we consider both more relevant and where the implementation is expected not to be too difficult and time-consuming.

It should be stressed that the issue about choosing not too time-consuming implementations applies to the parts to be accomplished within the present MDMC Master work, due to its time constraints. We expect however to continue the work on the NOMAD parsers also after the end of this Master thesis, addressing some further extension possibilities among those already

found, or possible new ones which may emerge.

3.1.1 Extension opportunities

In this subsection I will list some possible extensions to the NOMAD parsers, as of end 2024 / beginning 2025, that we have found as an outcome of the above-mentioned code-specific NOMAD hands-on sessions, arranged by simulation code.

For QuantumEspresso:

- NOMAD does not produce band structure plots for QE, at a difference with its behaviour for other electronic structure codes
- NOMAD considers as QE mainfiles the *.out files produced by runs using the pw.x executable only, thus excluding the outputs of pp.x postprocessing runs

For Yambo:

- NOMAD does not write or display chemical composition, cell parameters, atom positions
- NOMAD does not plot spectra
- NOMAD yields error messages on our test upload of Yambo GW data

For Siesta:

- NOMAD does not plot band structures and density of states (DOS)
- NOMAD fails in parsing the “*xc_{author}*” string (related to the name of the chosen exchange-correlation [XC] functional)

For LAMMPS:

- NOMAD considers both log.* files and *.out files as LAMMPS mainfiles. The *.out file generally contains less info than the log.* one: this can result in entries lacking some information on the system, when based on a *.out file as mainfile
- cell parameters, MD trajectory etc are displayed only in some cases (by inspecting already present uploads and performing new uploads of our data)

3.2 Objectives

For choosing the items to address within this work, among those listed above, we have focused on the codes most of us in the NFFA-DI UMIL Theo&Sim group are using, resulting in the following list:

- 1) Plotting QE band structures
- 2) solving the NOMAD error on Yambo GW files
- 3) reporting and displaying Yambo cell parameters and chemical composition in the OVERVIEW page
- 4) plotting Yambo spectra
- 5) displaying at least some of the relevant physical quantities from Siesta runs

In Chapter 4 I will describe the work I have performed, in collaboration with our internship student Hajar Belgroun and our postdoc colleague Masoumeh Alihosseini and in close contact with the NOMAD developers, on the mentioned items. Of course it must be kept in mind that we have performed (and we are still performing) this "extension" work on the currently available "old" version of the computational parsers, not on the new version which is still under development. We have been driven to this choice by our internal rather strict time deadlines, in order to be able to perform, as is usual in this type of work, several rounds of coding and debugging, testing our code changes on our local Oasis, for several parsers, within the time frame of the present MDMC master project. We may however envisage a possible future collaboration with the FAIRmat team on the transition to the new plugin-based schema, with contributions on our side for the parts we have implemented in the current parsers.

In addition to these NOMAD-related objectives, I will mention here further tasks which are envisaged within my MDMC project, namely the writing or updating of the Data Management Plans and Interactive Remote Access forms for the computational techniques offered by the UMIL Theo&Sim lab to external users through NFFA-DI user calls. The work I have performed on these tasks will also be described in Chapter 4.

Chapter 4

Results

In this Chapter I will describe the work I have done so far on the implementation of new functionalities in the NOMAD parsers for some of the codes we use in the UMIL Theo&Sim lab. I have performed this work with local contributions from our internship undergraduate student Hajar Belgroun and from our postdoc colleague Masoumeh Alihosseini, and in close collaboration with several members of the FAIRmat NOMAD team.

Moreover I will also report on further tasks I have performed, namely the preparation of Data Management Plans and Interactive Remote Access forms for our UMIL Theo&Sim techniques and the installation of a NOMAD Oasis. Also these tasks are part of the data management activity for our UMIL Theo&Sim lab, although not related to NOMAD.

4.1 Data Management Plans and Interactive Remote Access forms

For the NFFA-DI project a hierarchical organization of Data Management Plans has been chosen (as explained in the NFFA-DI D1.2 Deliverable), consisting of three levels:

- 1) a general NFFA-DI DMP, defining the data management guidelines for the whole project, both regarding the handling and storing of research data, by the use of a common repository, and regarding the policy on scientific publications

- 2) Lab-DMPs for the various laboratories within the NFFA-DI distributed RI, outlining the specific data management strategies for the instrumentation and techniques available at the specific labs, and the roles and responsibilities of the persons in charge of the FAIR-by-design treatment of research data

(Data Curators); these lab-DMPs will have to comply with the general data management policies stated in the general NFFA-DI DMP. We point out that most laboratories within NFFA-DI include more than a single instrument or technique. In practice a DMP has to be prepared for each experimental or computational technique-instrument or technique-code combination: indeed different experimental instruments or simulation codes can be available at a single lab or at different labs for the same technique, and on the other hand - at least for the computational labs this is certainly the case - a single "instrument" (simulation code) can be used to perform different types of "techniques" (simulations)

3) Proposal-DMPs for each of the approved NFFA-DI user projects. Each proposal-DMP will be written by the Principal Investigator (PI) of the corresponding user project and will have to comply with the data management policies stated in the lab-DMP of the laboratory where the project will be carried out.

The choice of such a hierarchical structure ensures coherence among the various DMPs and moreover it is aimed at facilitating the task of writing the DMP both for researchers which are in charge of the individual instruments and - even more - for external users as PIs of approved user projects, avoiding unnecessary duplications.

All these DMPs, from the general NFFA-DI one to the lab-DMPs and Proposal-DMPs, are to be considered *living documents*, i.e. they will be updated when necessary. In order to further simplify the task for external users, the use of a form on the NFFA-DI SEP is envisaged for Proposal-DMPs: the form will already contain the information on the type and format of data and metadata derived from the lab-DMPs of the chosen instruments/techniques, so that the Proposal PIs will only have to add information on the data management for their specific research project.

As mentioned in Chapter 2, the UMIL OU of NFFA-DI consists of an experimental and a computational part. In this Master project I am taking care of data management and curation activities for the computational part: this includes also the writing of DMPs for each of the UMIL Theo&Sim computational "techniques" as classified on the catalog on the NFFA-DI Single Entry Point and explained in Chapter 2. Thanks to the above-mentioned hierarchical structure of the DMPs in the NFFA-DI project, with lower level DMPs "inheriting" the general parts from higher level ones, and to the fact that in our UMIL Theo&Sim lab the "techniques" simply correspond to different simulation codes, writing the DMPs for the UMIL Theo&Sim lab was quite straightforward, in that the "free" fields to be filled were relatively few.

Coming to the specificities related to our computational "techniques", the following points are worth mentioning:

A) several fields in the forms for NFFA-DI lab-DMPs are dealing with technical features of experimental instruments, and are therefore unapplicable to computational techniques and simulation codes

B) all the simulation codes our UMIL Theo&Sim lab is offering to external users are open source codes, and accordingly their input and output files are not in proprietary format: they are either simple text files, which can be opened with any text editor, or binary files in hdf5 format, which can be parsed with any tool which handles such format. This is in agreement with the general data policy of the NFFA-DI project, and we have mentioned it in our DMPs

C) as already explained, NOMAD has been chosen within NFFA-DI as the repository for computational research data. This was therefore mentioned in all our UMIL Theo&Sim DMPs

D) as explained above, lab-DMPs are to be prepared for each technique - instrument/code combination. In the UMIL Theo&Sim lab, as illustrated in Chapter 2, the codes and techniques we are offering through the NFFA-DI catalog are: QuantumEspresso for SGSEP (Structural and Ground State Electronic Properties) and MP (Magnetic Properties), Siesta for the same two techniques, TranSiesta for TP (Transport Properties), Yambo for ESP (Excited State Properties) and LAMMPS for AMM (Atoms and Molecules in Motion). Accordingly, I have prepared a lab-DMP for each of these technique/code combinations, resulting in a total of seven lab-DMPs. For this task, I have started from preliminary versions of the DMPs included in the D5.3 NFFA-DI Deliverable, which in turn had been filled based on the information we had put in the NFFA-DI catalog for our techniques in the Theory & Simulation installation (<https://nffa-di.it/en/our-offer/#installation-10104>). Starting from this material, I have verified together with the involved colleagues the specific information on the various codes and techniques and updated it (and/or the information present on the NFFA-DI catalog) if necessary. Based on what has been explained and discussed so far, these 7 lab-DMPs differ from each other in few fields, i.e. the name of the Instrument Scientist, the size of generated data, the name of the technique and its description.

The Interactive Remote Access (IRA) forms are another set of documents related to the DMPs and to the NFFA-DI Data Management policy in general. The protocol for Interactive Remote Access by external users (through approved Proposals) to NFFA-DI experimental and computational resources has been delineated in the NFFA-DI D6.1 deliverable within Work Package 6 (WP6). The general aim is to ensure the possibility for external users of having remote access to NFFA-DI facilities within their user projects without the need of physically travelling to the chosen NFFA-DI OU. This

provides obvious advantages e.g. in terms of costs and of the sustainability of the NFFA-DI research infrastructure as a whole (through reduction of CO₂ emissions).

There can be several different levels and types of Remote Access to a research infrastructure such as NFFA-DI, including connecting to the computers at the OU labs through ssh, ftp, vpn etc, and remote access to experimental instrumentation. This latter can be either in the form of full and autonomous remote access by external users to the experimental instrument, including direct control of the instrument (which however can be challenging due to the specificity of the instrumentation available at the various NFFA-DI OUs and the expertise required for its use) or through Interactive Remote Access, where remote instrument control is not essential, but there is a remote connection of the external user with the on-site operator who directly operates the instrumentation. IRA has been chosen as the basic protocol for external user access to NFFA-DI facilities within user projects, with the direct remote connection of the user to the instrument as a possible further level to be implemented in selected cases.

The information on the availability of IRA and/or of direct remote access has therefore been included among the various fields in the technique descriptions in the NFFA-DI online catalog of techniques, and it can be selected by interested external users upon preparing their proposals for applying to user calls. This information on Remote Access has been asked to each of the NFFA-DI OUs through specific forms to be filled, and I have filled the IRA forms for all the technique/code combinations available at UMIL Theo&Sim lab.

For the UMIL Theo&Sim lab the whole issue of remote access is much less technically challenging, but also less relevant, with respect to the case of experimental Installations, for several reasons:

i) remote access to a computational lab which offers the use of open source simulation codes simply means remote access to the computers used by the lab to run simulations, and on which the needed codes are already installed and available. This can easily be put in place (if required) by simply creating accounts for the external users on our computers/clusters. All the technically challenging issues involved in remotely running experiments, such as e.g. automatic positioning of samples, are absent in the computational case.

ii) in our UMIL Theo&Sim lab, we run a significant part of our simulations (due to their rather large memory and parallelization requirements) on external computing facilities, in particular on CINECA (<https://www.hpc.cineca.it/>) High Performance Computing (HPC) machines, rather than on our internal computers/clusters. In these cases, the relevant issue, if external

users wish to autonomously run their simulations, is access to e.g. CINECA machines, rather than access to our UMIL Theo&Sim computers.

iii) from our experience in the analogous NFFA Europe Pilot (NEP) project, on which we have had several user projects assigned to our UMIL Theo&Sim lab, we know that the most likely scenario (the only one we have encountered so far, indeed) for computational user projects is the one where proposals are submitted by experimental research groups (generally with no experience in simulations), who ask us to perform specific simulations in order to help interpret some of their experimental results. This is quite different from the case of proposals applying for access to experimental techniques, which are generally submitted by experimentalists, possibly even experts of the particular technique to which they are applying, and thus possibly interested in and capable of running the measurements autonomously, in a similar scenario to that of applying for measurement time at a Large Scale Facility (LSF).

Summarizing the above discussion, we may say that, while experimental NFFA-DI Installations offer specific state-of-the-art instrumentation - together with local expertise in those specific, sometimes customized, instruments - often to experimentalists who know how to use at least similar instruments, on the other hand what we offer as UMIL Theo&Sim lab is our expertise - as users and in some cases also developers - in performing a certain range of simulation types using a certain range of open source simulation codes, not the use of specific codes (which is available to everyone since they are open source) or the access to our local computers (which at most can be a byproduct). Therefore in our case it is rather unlikely that external users will be interested in remote access to our computers, either for directly running their simulations or for visualizing and analyzing the results. However, in case this happens, it can be easily done by creating user accounts on our machines for our proposal users. Accordingly, after discussing the matter both with my colleagues ("Instrument Scientists" of the various computational techniques) and with the NFFA-DI colleagues in charge of WP6, I have answered "yes" to the question of remote control, specifying ssh as the used protocol, for all our technique/code combinations.

4.2 NOMAD Oasis

Then, as a general task which is needed for all subsequent work on NOMAD parsers, I have successfully installed an Oasis, i.e. a local NOMAD instance, on my work pc at UMIL Theo&Sim lab, by following the instruc-

tions provided by our MDMC Theo&Sim tutors during a dedicated online workshop held in January 2025. All the test uploads related to the work described in the following have been performed on this local "personal" Oasis. In the meantime I have been in contact with our IT colleagues of the Physics Department in order to have a group Oasis for the UMIL Theo&Sim lab installed on a dedicated department Virtual Machine: this has involved exchanges of information on the hardware and software requirements etc. The UMIL Theo&Sim group Oasis has finally been installed in April 2025 by our IT colleagues, and we still have to test it and create users.

4.3 QE band structure plotting

As mentioned in 3.1.1 and 3.2, NOMAD did not plot band structures from QuantumEspresso as of end of 2024, at a difference with its behaviour for other electronic structure codes, e.g. FHIaims and Exciting (see Figures 4.1 and 4.2). Band structure calculations are among the most common types of calculations performed in the ab initio characterization of periodic extended systems (mainly bulk crystals and surfaces). They provide important information on the electronic properties of the investigated systems and can be directly compared to experimentally measured Angle Resolved PhotoEmission Spectra (ARPES).

Therefore we have chosen the implementation of QE band structure plotting as one of the issues on which to focus in view of enhancing the NOMAD functionalities related to the codes of common use in the UMIL Theo&Sim lab. Indeed this was already among the subjects we had discussed in an online meeting with colleagues of other italian research institutions and companies and with representatives of the FAIRmat NOMAD team, aimed at assessing the development state in NOMAD electronic-parsers of several features some of us were interested in having implemented (including also the parsing of Electron Paramagnetic Resonance and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance calculations, to which other groups in the meeting were particularly interested).

After that first "global" meeting, I devoted my attention to band structure plotting in QE, which had turned out to be of high interest/priority only for our UMIL Theo&Sim lab. To this aim, together with our internship student Hajar Belgroun, I have started inspecting the parts regarding the parsing of band structures in the NOMAD parsers for those electronic structure codes in which this functionality is present, in order to identify which variables, classes etc should be added in the QE parser to achieve the desired behaviour.

We have thus found that, among those codes for which band structures are

Figure 4.1: Screenshots from the NOMAD entry `rQn4Umvd5uaEljmudVbI6asU3_FK`, a band structure calculation with the FHIaims code, showing: the band structure plot in the OVERVIEW page (upper panel), and the subsection `properties.electronic.band structure electronic` in the DATA page (lower panel).

Figure 4.2: Screenshots from our upload of a QuantumEspresso band structure calculation, showing: no band structure plot in the OVERVIEW page (upper panel), and no subsection properties.electronic.band structure electronic in the DATA page (lower panel).

plotted in NOMAD, for the FHIaims code there is a `bandstructure_parser` class, of type `DataTextParser`; instead for the Exciting code there are a `bandstructure_dat_parser` of type `DataTextParser` and a `bandstructure_parser` of type `BandstructureXMLParser`. By looking at raw files from NOMAD uploads of both the mentioned codes (we had no in-house examples, since we are not using those codes in our group) we have understood that this difference is related to the fact that band structure calculations performed with the Exciting code produce two different band structure output files, a plain text one and an xml one.

This was indeed our first in-depth approach to the NOMAD parsers and more in general to the structure of the NOMAD code, and we have been spending some time in trying to understand the general organization of the code, where one of the main features is the distinction between:

A) classes, functions etc of general use, defined in the general part of NOMAD (in <https://github.com/nomad-coe/nomad/tree/develop/nomad>)

B) software package-specific parsers (in <https://github.com/nomad-coe/electronic-parsers/tree/develop/electronicparsers> for electronic structure codes) - e.g. in this case the parsers for the Exciting code and for the FHIaims code - with their "derived" classes, functions etc, inheriting properties and methods from the ones in the general part of NOMAD .

Moreover, this first approach has made clear to us that the "exporting" of parts of NOMAD code from the parser of a given software package (in our present example FHIaims or Exciting) in order to use them for implementing the same feature for a different simulation software can be less straightforward than expected, mainly due to the often rather different formats in which the same physical quantities are stored in the output files of different simulation codes. Different formats in the raw files naturally lead to different choices on how to handle these data in the parser.

With *different formats* we refer here both to the distinction e.g. between plain text files and binary files, but also, within the class of text files, to the detailed arrangement in which the given quantities are reported: this is relevant in particular for quantities which can be represented as vectors, rather than for single numerical values.

Band structures are an emblematic example: the output of a band structure calculation consists in, for each of the examined bands, a series of (point in k space, Energy) pairs, where the points in k space are chosen so to build a path which connects high symmetry points for that specific crystal structure (e.g. face centered cubic, hexagonal, ...) in reciprocal space. By looking at the band structure output files produced by several electronic structure codes, we find that, for instance, in QuantumEspresso band structure calcu-

```

&plot nbnd= 8, nks= 36 /
  0.500000 0.500000 0.500000
-3.418 -0.822 5.029 5.029 7.814 9.597 9.597 13.838
  0.400000 0.400000 0.400000
-3.891 -0.102 5.102 5.102 7.900 9.679 9.679 13.959
  0.300000 0.300000 0.300000
-4.659 1.404 5.319 5.319 8.138 9.803 9.803 13.845
  0.200000 0.200000 0.200000
-5.285 3.222 5.660 5.660 8.504 9.636 9.636 12.333
  0.100000 0.100000 0.100000
-5.678 5.104 6.050 6.050 8.848 9.120 9.120 10.612
  0.000000 0.000000 0.000000
-5.810 6.255 6.255 6.255 8.822 8.822 8.822 9.723
  0.000000 0.000000 0.100000
-5.767 5.981 6.072 6.072 8.710 9.057 9.057 9.984
  0.000000 0.000000 0.200000
-5.634 5.334 5.660 5.660 8.424 9.630 9.630 10.519
  0.000000 0.000000 0.300000
-5.413 4.527 5.186 5.186 8.052 10.370 10.370 10.706

```

Figure 4.3: Part of a file showing one of the possible formats in which band structure data can be stored in QE files.

```

0.0000 -3.4180
0.1732 -3.8910
0.3464 -4.6593
0.5196 -5.2849
0.6928 -5.6783
0.8660 -5.8099
0.9660 -5.7668
(.....)
3.7146 -4.4382
3.8560 -5.0244
3.9974 -5.4577
4.1388 -5.7218
4.2802 -5.8099

0.0000 -0.8220
0.1732 -0.1018
0.3464 1.4042
0.5196 3.2219
0.6928 5.1037
0.8660 6.2549

```

Figure 4.4: Part of a file showing another one of the possible formats in which band structure data can be stored in QE files.

lations, a band structure is first stored as a list of lines of alternating type: one line consisting of three numbers (the 3D coordinate of a given k point) followed by a line listing the energy values of the N chosen bands at that k point (Figure 4.3).

Then, by running a postprocessing tool, the band structure data can be converted into a sequence of $(\text{dist}(i), \text{energy}(i))$ pairs of vectors (" i " being an index counting the steps in k space making up the path), written as two columns of numbers, where each of these pairs of vectors corresponds to a band and pairs of vectors of consecutive bands (from lower to higher energy states) are separated by an empty line in the file (Figure 4.4): in these files " dist " is not a given point in k space, but the distance covered up to that point, with respect to the initial point in the k space path.

It is worth stressing that the two discussed formats do not simply differ in "expectable" ways, like for example choosing to list the components of a vector either as a row or as a column of numbers, but also involve a different way of identifying each of the points which compose the k space path, namely either by its 3 coordinates or by the total length in k space which has been covered, along the chosen path, up to that point.

Further different arrangements of band structure data are possible, and sometimes a single electronic structure code (e.g. QuantumEspresso, as already mentioned above) can produce different band structure files with different formats. I have mentioned these two format examples only to highlight the hidden complexity that often collides with the intuitive expectation of easy exporting of a specific functionality from the NOMAD parser for a given simulation code to the parsers for several other codes.

This inhomogeneity of formats for the same physical quantity obtained through different simulation codes is, as discussed in the preceding chapters, one of the main motivations for having platforms like NOMAD which convert all these data to a common hierarchical structure, with a common vocabulary etc, but at the same time it makes the coding of specific parsers challenging.

After this first study of the band structure parts within some electronic structure parsers, I have made contact again with the FAIRmat team, this time through the NOMAD Discord channel (<https://discord.com/channels/1201445470485106719/1339151869196501022>), in order to ask for some clarifications on how to build a class for QE band structure parsing, from which general class to let it inherit methods etc. From this discussion it has come out that one of the members of the FAIRmat NOMAD team (Nathan Daelman) was already at a very advanced stage in developing this feature, having already made a Pull Request (PR) for his implementation (<https://github.com/nomad-coe/electronic-parsers/pull/279>), Fig. 4.5, 4.6. So we have deemed that trying to do something similar on our part

would have been a waste of human resources, and would also be contrary to the general principle of "not reinventing the wheel each time", namely to try to re-use and adapt existing tools, pieces of code etc as much as possible, avoiding unnecessary duplications.

Therefore we have decided to contribute to this effort by being available for testing it and for discussing possible issues which may emerge, taking advantage of our knowledge on the scientific side of the problem and our practical experience on using QE. Indeed we have provided N. Daelman with some QE band structure folders for testing purposes, and discussed with him about where to find the information about the Fermi energy in QE files, to be used for setting the zero of the energy in the band structure plots, and on how to proceed in those cases when E_{Fermi} is not written in QE files (a reasonable and quite common way is to use the top valence energy instead). Once this issue has been made clear, N. Daelman's implementation of band structure parsing and plotting from QE files is expected to be soon included in the general NOMAD.

4.4 Yambo GW calculations

The errors in parsing GW outputs from Yambo have been the second subject we have decided to investigate. Upon uploading a folder consisting in a QE ground state calculation, followed by a Yambo setup run (with its r_{setup} mainfile) and Yambo GW and BSE runs (each with its r^* mainfiles and some additional output o^* files containing respectively GW corrections and BSE spectra) all on a magnetic molecule[19], NOMAD had failed to create an entry for the Yambo GW r^* file (while it created entries for the QE *.out file, and for the other Yambo r^* files). This was accompanied by an error message in the LOGS page, regarding two values expected and only one found, in the parsing of Quasi Particle (QP) corrections. I recall here that r^* files, i.e. Yambo log files, containing the values of the input variables, and information of the various steps of the performed calculation, are considered by NOMAD as Yambo *mainfiles* (similarly to *.out files for QuantumEspresso) and as such they are mandatory in order for NOMAD to create an archive for uploaded data. Relevant output data for Yambo calculations can be contained either in the r^* files themselves or in the o^* files, depending on the type of calculation (e.g. spectra are contained in o^* files, GW corrections both in r^* and in o^* files).

Also in this case I have contacted the FAIRmat team on the Discord channel (<https://discord.com/channels/1201445470485106719/1201454263260413992/threads/1348983787018653777>) to ask for advice, since

```

21 22 import re
23
48 49 Stress,
49 50 StressEntry,
50 51 Thermodynamics,
51 - BandEnergies,
52 52 ScfIteration,
53 53 Dos,
54 54 DosValues,
55 + BandEnergies,
56 + BandGapDeprecated,
57 + BandStructure,
58 )
59 from simulationworkflowschema import (
60     SinglePoint,
61
62     Stress,
63     StressEntry,
64     Thermodynamics,
65     ScfIteration,
66     Dos,
67     DosValues,
68     BandEnergies,
69     BandGapDeprecated,
70     BandStructure,
71     SinglePoint,
72 )
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```

Figure 4.5: A part of N. Daelman’s implementation of band structure parsing in the NOMAD QE parser, to which we have collaborated by discussing from which QE outputs to extract band structure data, where to find the Fermi energy value etc, and by providing test QE band structure data.

our file with the QP corrections was not corrupt and moreover it was not clear at all what these two expected values vs. one value found mentioned in

```

filter - Conversations - [icon]
202 [icon] electronicparsers/quantumpresso/parser.py [icon]
2802 +     'band',
2803 +     r'point group:([\s\S]+?)\n\n',
2804 +     repeats=True,
2805 +     sub_parser=TextParser{
2806 +         quantities=[
2807 +             Quantity{
2808 +                 'energy',
2809 +                 r'e\[\s*\d+ \s*\d+\] =\s*{[\-\d\.\.]+}\s+eV',
2810 +                 repeats=True,
2811 +                 dtype=Float, # unit (eV) should be specified later
2812 +             },
2813 +             Quantity{
2814 +                 'mult',
2815 +                 r'eV\s*(\d+)\s*-->',
2816 +                 repeats=True,
2817 +                 dtype=int,
2818 +             },
2819 +         ],
2820 +     },
2821 + },
2822 + ]
2823 +
2824 + @staticmethod

```

```

202 [icon] electronicparsers/quantumpresso/parser.py [icon]
2825 + @staticmethod
2826 + def match_header(line: str) -> bool:
2827 +     pattern = re.compile(
2828 +         r'Program BANDS v\.\d+\.\d+ starts on \d+\w+\d+ at \d+:\d+:\d+'
2829 +     )
2830 +     return True if pattern.search(line) else False
2831 +
2832 + @staticmethod
2833 + def points_to_segments(kpoints: list, symmetries: list) -> list[list[list[float]]]:
2834 +     """Split the kpoints by segment based on differing symmetry group."""
2835 +
2836 +     def shift_window(window: tuple, elem) -> tuple:
2837 +         return window[1:] + (elem,)
2838 +
2839 +     previous_point: Optional[list[float]] = None
2840 +     symmetry_window: tuple[Optional[str]] = (None,) * 3
2841 +
2842 +     segments: list[list[np.ndarray[float]]] = [[]]
2843 +     for point, symmetry in zip(kpoints, symmetries):
2844 +         symmetry_window = shift_window(symmetry_window, symmetry)
2845 +         # case enumeration for 'symmetry_window':
2846 +         # 1. {None, None, None} -> not possible

```

Figure 4.6: A further part of N. Daelman’s implementation of band structure parsing in the NOMAD QE parser.

the error message may be. Indeed both the r^* and the o^* files of the Yambo GW run contain (after a header and/or a longer text part reporting the used

input variables and several characteristics of the system) the list of the computed GW corrections to all the selected energy levels. These corrections are arranged in a series of lines, one line corresponding to a single energy level, and consisting of several columns containing (in different formats in the r^* vs o^* file) data such as the index of the energy level, the k point index, the Independent Particle energy value, the GW correction, the resulting QP-corrected energy value. In collaboration with the NOMAD developers, it has been found that this kind of error only happened for spin-polarized systems (our chosen test upload was indeed a spin-polarized system, a magnetic molecule: iron phthalocyanine), due to the fact that, in the general NOMAD distribution as of end of 2024 / beginning of 2025, the part of the Yambo parser involving the parsing of GW data did not take into account the possibility of having two separate spin channels. A. N. Ladines (NOMAD team) has implemented a fix for this specific issue, so to allow for either one or two spin channels in the parsing of the QP corrections, and we have tested this fix on our already mentioned spin-polarized GW upload, confirming its correct behaviour, i.e. the absence of error messages in the LOGS page. This fix is now included in the general NOMAD.

Of course, having eliminated the parsing errors for spin-polarized GW calculations, it would be desirable to have NOMAD plot the GW-corrected band structure (for extended systems), which it currently does not do. Plotting the GW-corrected band structure superimposed with the one obtained by a simple Independent Particle calculation is a common practice in the community, in order to visualize how and to what extent the inclusion of the QuasiParticle corrections affects the electronic structure of the investigated system.

It is worth stressing that, as of end of 2024 / beginning of 2025, GW-corrected bands are just one out of a series of physical quantities that are not yet reported in NOMAD Yambo uploads. We have therefore decided to focus first on implementing the parsing and displaying of more basic and general interest properties, among those still missing, i.e. starting with the chemical composition and simulation cell (see next subsection).

4.5 Yambo cell parameters

As already mentioned in previous sections, we had noticed that, both for our test Yambo uploads and for several Yambo entries from other authors we examined on NOMAD, no information on cell parameters, atom positions and chemical composition was written, and no image of the system atoms within the unit cell was shown, either in the OVERVIEW page or

in the FILES page, at a difference with the behaviour for other simulations codes e.g. QuantumEspresso. Moreover, Yambo entries also displayed a "no representative section system found" warning in the LOGS page.

At first we thought this may be due to the current NOMAD Yambo parser lacking some variables describing cell, atom positions and chemical composition, but, by inspecting the parser, we found that such variables are indeed present.

Then, by looking, together with our postdoc colleague Masoumeh Alihosseini, at the NOMAD Yambo tests (<https://github.com/nomad-coe/electronic-parsers/tree/develop/tests/data/yambo>), we have realized that indeed NOMAD is capable of parsing and writing/displaying cell parameters and chemical composition from Yambo files, provided the upload contains a ns.db file, contained in a /SAVE subfolder, in addition to the mandatory r* mainfile, as is the case for the hBN Yambo test. On the other hand, all the contributed Yambo uploads we examined on the general NOMAD had no /SAVE/ns.db file, and accordingly they did not display geometric and chemical information. We have then further tested this feature by uploading Yambo data of ours, both containing a ns.db file in the main folder or in a /SAVE subfolder (the latter is the default folder structure for Yambo calculations): only in the latter case did NOMAD display the cell with the atoms, write cell parameters and chemical composition.

Despite the presence in the NOMAD Yambo test folder of Yambo uploads containing ns.db files in a /SAVE subfolder, the need for ns.db files in order to be able to display geometric and chemical information was not explicitly documented with enough visibility for potential users, as witnessed also by the fact that most (if not all) of the existing Yambo uploads on NOMAD do not contain ns.db files and therefore do not display the system atoms in the simulation cell and the chemical composition. As a result of our interaction with the NOMAD team on this subject, this requirement is now mentioned, with a direct link to my detailed Discord thread (<https://discord.com/channels/1201445470485106719/1208029192881442866/threads/1351201658440519761>), in the NOMAD GitHub, in the Issues section for electronic-parsers: <https://github.com/nomad-coe/electronic-parsers/issues>, and it is going to be handled by the NOMAD team in the near future by possibly letting NOMAD issue a warning in case the ns.db file is missing.

By inspecting the NOMAD Yambo parser, we have understood that NOMAD reads the data which are more related to the results (e.g. calculated energies) from the r* mainfile, and "input" data related to the geometry and chemical composition from the ns.db file, using two different parsing functions.

While testing the parsing and writing of cell parameters from Yambo

uploads, and the requisites regarding the ns.db file, we have made uploads of several different Yambo calculations performed in our UMIL Theo&Sim lab, for different physical systems, both isolated molecules and extended systems. We have thus found that in several cases NOMAD yields an error related to the number of atom coordinates not matching the number of atoms (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.7: Screenshots of the FILES (left) and LOGS (right) sections of a Yambo upload of ours on the NOMAD, showing respectively: left: the mismatch between the reported total number of atoms indicated in the Species and Labels variables and that reported in the Positions variable; right: the corresponding error message in the LOGS section.

By careful inspection of our Yambo files (in particular the r^* mainfiles and the ns.db files) for the various examined systems, we have understood the origin of this error, and the reason why it is present only in some cases. The Yambo code, upon reading from the previous QE calculation the data about geometry and chemical composition of the system, stores several quantities: total number of atoms, number of chemical species, number of atoms for each chemical species, maximum number of atoms per chemical species, atom coordinates, etc. We have already mentioned that the NOMAD Yambo parser reads these geometric and chemical quantities from the ns.db file, which is, however, a binary file: its only human-readable parts are section headers, among which e.g. *ATOM_POS*, *MAX_ATOMS*. Some of these quantities are also present in the r^* mainfiles, but often the list of coordinates is not. So, in order to examine directly the cause of the mentioned mismatch, we need to be able to read the contents of the ns.db file. This is in HDF5 format, and we have therefore taken from this site <https://docs.h5py.org/en/stable/quick.html> a python script which

converts such files to text, and our internship student Hajar Belgroun has partially modified it to adapt to our needs.

```

735
736         # read structure data from netcdf input file
737         self.netcdf_parser.mainfile = os.path.join(
738             self.maindir, self.mainfile_parser.cpu_files_io.input.file
739         )
740         if self.netcdf_parser.mainfile is not None:
741             system = System()
742             run.system.append(system)
743             positions = self.netcdf_parser.get('ATOM_POS', [])
744             max_n_atoms = self.netcdf_parser.get('MAX_ATOMS')
745             n_atoms = self.netcdf_parser.N_ATOMS
746             atom_numbers = np.hstack(
747                 [
748                     [self.netcdf_parser.atomic_numbers[int(n)]] * int(n_atoms[int(n)])
749                     for n in range(len(n_atoms))
750                 ]
751             )
752
753     # we define the process_and_select function within the parse_input function
754     def process_and_select(positions, max_n_atoms, n_atoms):
755
756         positions = np.array(positions)
757         blocks = []
758         selected = []
759
760         positions = positions.reshape(-1, 3)
761
762

```

Figure 4.8: A part of our modified version of the NOMAD Yambo parser, with two different variables max_n_atoms and n_atoms used for the maximum number of atoms per chemical species among all the chemical species present in the investigated system and for the actual number of atoms for each chemical species present, respectively.

By applying this tool to the ns.db files of our test Yambo uploads we have been able to ascertain the reason for the mentioned error. Namely, Yambo uses the "maximum n. of atoms per chemical species" quantity (max_n_atoms) to build one $3 \times (max_n_atoms)$ -sized matrix for each chemical species present in the system, for then storing the atom coordinates in these matrices in the ns.db file. Yambo is thus sizing all these matrices based on the size needed for the largest of them, and then filling only the first $n_atoms(spec_i)$ lines of each of them with the atom coordinates read from

```

762         n_points = positions.shape[0]
763         n_blocks = int( int(n_points) // int(max_n_atoms) )
764
765         for i in range(n_blocks):
766             start_idx = int(i) * int(max_n_atoms)
767             end_idx = (int(i) + 1) * int(max_n_atoms)
768             block = positions[start_idx:end_idx]
769             blocks.append(block)
770
771
772         for i, block in enumerate(blocks):
773             n_to_select = int(n_atoms[int(i)])
774             selected_from_block = block[:n_to_select]
775             for point in selected_from_block:
776                 selected.append(point)
777
778         positions=np.array(selected)
779
780         return positions
781
782     positions = process_and_select(positions, max_n_atoms, n_atoms)
783
784
785     system.atoms = Atoms(
786         positions = positions * ureg.bohr,
787         labels=[chemical_symbols[int(n)] for n in atom_numbers],
788     )

```

Figure 4.9: A further part of our modified version of the NOMAD Yambo parser, showing first the division of the whole (wrong, oversized) list of coordinates into blocks corresponding to the different chemical species, and then the selection of only n_atoms lines, corresponding to the actual number of atoms for each of the chemical species present, from each of these blocks.

the previous QE calculation, where $n_atoms(spec_i)$ is the number of atoms of each chemical species $spec_i$ present in the system, leaving the exceeding lines filled with zeros. When NOMAD parses these lists of atom coordinates, in those cases where the system has different numbers of atoms for different chemical species, it finds that some of the chemical species present have a larger number of coordinates lines with respect to the number of atoms for that species (which is also extracted from the ns.db file), hence the error.

We have therefore added a part of code in the Yambo parser that handles this issue (Figures 4.8 and 4.9). In it we first divide the whole (wrong, oversized) list of coordinates into blocks of max_n_atoms lines each, cor-

responding to the different chemical species present in the system; then we select, for each chemical species, only the first n_atoms lines (containing the coordinates of the actually present atoms for that chemical species) and finally we re-assemble the lines so extracted into the final corrected coordinate list.

VALUE			
0.82350	1.03845	-0.15405	
-0.82294	0.60983	-0.05145	

Figure 4.10: Screenshot of a Yambo upload on our local NOMAD Oasis, showing the correct writing of the system chemical composition and displaying of atoms and simulation cell, obtained for a molecule with different number of atoms of different chemical species, by using our modified version of the Yambo parser.

We have then tested our modified Yambo parsers on uploads with either the same or different number of atoms for the different chemical species present in the system, showing the correct behaviour of our implementation in both these situations (see Figure 4.10 for an example with different numbers of atoms of different chemical species).

Finally, we have contacted the FAIRmat team on the NOMAD Discord channel, informing them of our implementation. Following their instructions, we have made a Pull Request (PR) of our fork, containing our modified Yambo parser, and, as requested, we have also uploaded an example Yambo folder for this feature in the NOMAD Yambo test directory and added the corresponding part of code in `test_yamboparser.py` ([https://github.com/emolteni/electronic-parsers/blob/develop/tests/\\$test_yambopar](https://github.com/emolteni/electronic-parsers/blob/develop/tests/$test_yambopar)

[ser.py](#)). Our PR is now being evaluated by the FAIRmat team.

4.6 Yambo spectra

As already mentioned, as of end 2024 / beginning 2025 Yambo spectra were not plotted by NOMAD. As a first step towards implementing the plotting of Yambo spectra, we have checked, by inspecting the Sections and Subsections listed in the FILES (or DATA) page of NOMAD uploads, that a SpectroscopicProperties subsection, with a further sub-subsection Spectra, is foreseen under Results.Properties.

Then we have inspected uploads of spectra from other NOMAD-supported electronic structure codes, in order to check for which of these NOMAD is able to parse and plot spectra, and how this functionality is coded in the respective parsers. From our inspection of several NOMAD uploads of spectra, obtained both with Yambo and with other electronic structure codes, there seems to exist a general problem, not limited to Yambo but common also to the OCEAN, Exciting and QE-xspectra codes. For several uploads we have examined, for all of these three codes, spectra plots are not shown and the SpectroscopicProperties subsection is not present under Results.Properties. In the OCEAN, Exciting and QE-xspectra cases there is also a "Could not render spectroscopic properties" warning in the OVERVIEW page; this warning is absent in Yambo uploads.

For QE-xspectra, we have verified that this behaviour occurs only for "old" uploads (e.g. dating back to 2016), which had been parsed with old versions of the QE-xspectra parser. The current QE-xspectra parser instead, which is in the workflow-parsers folder of NOMAD (at a difference with the parsers for most of the other electronic structure codes, which are in the electronic-parsers folder) correctly parses and plots spectra. Moreover, in the QE-xspectra parser, "Spectra" is a subsection of Run.Calculation, as can be seen both in the parser itself and in the FILES page of QE-xspectra (recent) uploads, instead of being a subsection of Results.Properties.SpectroscopicProperties

This occurrence allows us to highlight a further element to be taken into account when aiming at verifying which features are present and which are missing on NOMAD for a given simulation code. The large amount of code making up the NOMAD "machinery" is under continuous development, both by the FAIRmat team and by user contributions, and this makes NOMAD increasingly useful and rich in features. On the other hand, NOMAD is also a *repository* of material science data - indeed each NOMAD upload becomes an "archive" in the NOMAD language - and, as a repository/archive, old uploads have been processed at the time of their upload, using the then available

(possibly incomplete or still under development) parsers, and stored as such, without being reprocessed when new versions of the parsers became available. This is exactly what we are used to in old-style paper archives, but we find it surprising when it happens in an online repository, since we are "trained" to expect online things to be always up-to-date. Based on this situation, we must keep in mind that the best way to check which functionalities are present in NOMAD for a given code is making new uploads, instead of simply checking what is displayed or not in the already existing ones.

```
class x_yambo_spectra(runschema.calculation.Spectra):
    m_def = Section(validate=False)

    x_yambo_output_spectra = Quantity(
        type=str,
        shape=[],
        description=" "
    )

    x_yambo_output_spectra_values = Quantity(
        type=np.float64,
        shape=[None, 3],
        description=" "
    )
```

Figure 4.11: Part of the `/yambo/metainfo/yambo.py` where we have defined "spectra" as a subsection of Calculation.

Coming back to the specific case of spectra in Yambo, we have decided to follow - at least partially - the implementation for spectra in the QE-xspectra parser, since QE-xspectra is a code for which we are sure that the current version of NOMAD is able to parse and plot spectra. So in particular we have defined Spectra as a subsection of Calculation, as it is in the QE-xspectra parser, instead of being a subsection of SpectroscopicProperties (which in turn is a subsection of Properties).

To this aim we have defined `x_yambo_spectra`, containing the quantities `x_yambo_spectra` and `x_yambo_output_spectra_values`, corresponding respectively to the header of the part in the `o*` file which lists excitation energies and imaginary and real part of the polarizability or dielectric function, and to the list of values themselves, as a subsection of `run.calculation` in the yambo metainfo (Fig. 4.11), and we have defined a corresponding quantity in the yambo parser.

This implementation is still in progress and we expect to conclude it after the end of this Master work. So far we have been able to obtain spectra plots from our Yambo data (Fig. 4.12) by running our modified parser (Fig. 4.13) locally on Jupyterlab (<https://jupyter.org/>). The corresponding part

Figure 4.12: A Yambo spectrum, plotted by using our local version, run on Jupyterlab, of our modified NOMAD Yambo parser where we have implemented an ad-hoc part for parsing and plotting spectra.

of code (with the needed changes, e.g. in how to tell NOMAD which file to read, and not explicitly coding the plotting) still does not work on our Oasis, i.e. it does not yield error or warning messages, but it does not produce plots either, and we still have to investigate whether this is due to syntax differences between Jupyterlab and the NOMAD parsers and metainfo code.

4.7 Siesta

As mentioned in Chapter 3, an inspection of Siesta uploads on NOMAD highlights a variety of extension possibilities for the Siesta parser, ranging from solving errors in reading the names of the used XC functionals to plotting density of states and band structures.

We have started to address some of these items, together with our UMIL postdoc colleague Masoumeh Alihosseini, who is now using Siesta for her calculations and has therefore some practical experience on this simulation code, in addition to a good knowledge of Python.

I am listing here the items we have addressed so far:

- 1) format problem in reading the names of the used exchange and cor-

```

#SECOND VERSION
import numpy as np
import re
from nomad.units import ureg
from nomad.datamodel.metainfo.simulation.calculation import Spectra
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

file_path = r"C:\Users\Hajar\Downloads\o-R_methylox_TDLDA.alpha_q1_slepc_ald_bse"
re_f = r'-?\d+\.\d+(?:[eE][+-]?\d+)?'

with open(file_path, 'r') as file:
    reading_output_file = file.read()

output_spectra = r'E/ev\[1\].*?Im\[2\].*?Re\[3\](.*?Im\[4\].*?Re\[5\])?'
header_match = re.search(output_spectra, reading_output_file)

if header_match:
    header = header_match.group(0)
    print('header', header)

    has_5_columns = bool(header_match.group(1))

    header_position = header_match.end()
    data_text = reading_output_file[header_position:]

    if has_5_columns:
        data_pattern = rf'\s*({re_f})\s+({re_f})\s+({re_f})\s+({re_f})\s+({re_f})'
    else:
        data_pattern = rf'\s*({re_f})\s+({re_f})\s+({re_f})'

    matches = re.finditer(data_pattern, data_text, re.MULTILINE)

    all_data = []
    for match in matches:
        row = [float(match.group(i)) for i in range(1, match.lastindex + 1)]
        all_data.append(row)

    all_data = np.array(all_data)

    spectra = Spectra(
        n_energies = all_data.shape[0],
        excitation_energies = all_data[:, 0] * ureg.eV,
        intensities = all_data[:, 1]
    )

    plt.plot(
        spectra.excitation_energies.magnitude,
        spectra.intensities
    )
    plt.xlabel("Excitation energy (eV)")
    plt.ylabel("Intensity")
    plt.title("Spectra")
    plt.grid(True)
    plt.show()

else:
    print("Header not found.")

```

Figure 4.13: Our local python code for parsing and plotting Yambo spectra.

relation (XC) functionals (xc_authors variable): we have fixed this it (Fig. 4.14), by allowing this data to be parsed either from the input file or from the output file (which is the "mainfile" for the Siesta parser). Indeed the NOMAD Siesta parser seemed to read no quantities from Siesta input files.


```

sec_method.dft = DFT(xc_functional=XCFunctional())
parameters = parameters.copy()

xc_label = parameters.get('xc_functional') or parameters.get('xc_check')

def get_xc_label():
    """
    Get the XC functional label from the FDF file.
    """
    with open(self.out_parser.mainfile, 'r') as f:
        content = f.read()
    import re
    matches = re.findall(r'XC_FUNCTIONAL[=]{1,2}([A-Z]{1,4})', content)
    if len(matches) >= 1:
        xc_label = matches[0].lower()
    else:
        raise Exception('Could not extract XC label from output file.')

    return xc_label

for xc_functional in self.xc_map.get(xc_label.lower(), []):
    if 'C' in xc_functional:
        sec_method.dft.xc_functional.exchange.append(Functional(name=xc_functional))
    elif 'D' in xc_functional:
        sec_method.dft.xc_functional.correlation.append(Functional(name=xc_functional))
    elif 'HYB' in xc_functional:
        sec_method.dft.xc_functional.hybrid.append(Functional(name=xc_functional))
    else:
        sec_method.dft.xc_functional.contributions.append(Functional(name=xc_functional))
else:
    self.logger.warning("Could not find any XC functional label in FDF or output.")
  
```

Figure 4.14: Part of the NOMAD Siesta parser which we have modified in order to solve the problems in reading the names of the used XC functionals. Note: the FDF file is the Siesta input file.

2) plotting electronic density of states (DOS): we have defined a new `dos_electronic_new` quantity, under `run.properties`, and added a part of code to parse the DOS for either the spin polarized or unpolarized case. This modified Siesta parser correctly parses DOS data and creates a plot in the OVERVIEW page. However it does not find the Fermi energy value, which would be needed to set the zero of the energy axis in the DOS plot, and accordingly NOMAD shows a warning about not being able to find the energy reference (Fig. 4.15): we plan to implement the use of E_{Fermi} for axis translation by inspecting the way this functionality is implemented for the VASP code, where NOMAD correctly creates DOS plots with $E - E_{Fermi}$ for the energy axis. Moreover, this part of the parser is not recognizing correctly spin-polarized vs unpolarized systems, and we still have to address this issue.

After finishing this part on the DOS, we plan to implement also the parsing and plotting of band structures from Siesta, partly based on our implementation for the DOS (band structures in Siesta are in a different file, but with a format similar to the DOS, i.e. simply columns of numerical data without text headers), and partly based on how band structure parsing is implemented for other codes, e.g. VASP or QuantumEspresso (for the latter, as mentioned above, N. Daelman from the FAIRmat team is just finishing implementing the band structure part, which was previously missing).

Figure 4.15: Screenshot of a Siesta DOS plot obtained by using our modified version of the Siesta parser on our Oasis. The DOS is plotted, but the parser is not yet using the Fermi energy value to fix the zero of the energy axis, and a warning is displayed about this.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and perspectives

In this project I have undertaken several tasks related to data management and curation for the computational part (UMIL Theo&Sim lab) of the UMIL Operative Unit of the NFFA-DI project.

The main part of the work has been devoted to implementing some extensions in the parsing of data and metadata from some of the simulation codes used in our lab by NOMAD, which is the platform chosen by NFFA-DI for the upload and storage of materials science data according to the FAIR principles.

In particular, for the plotting of QuantumEspresso band structures, not available in NOMAD as of end of 2024, I have been in contact with the FAIRmat NOMAD team, and have contributed to their implementation of this feature by discussing some specific items (use of Fermi energy or top valence energy for setting the energy zero in the plot, and where to find these data) and testing. This feature is expected to be soon available in the NOMAD platform.

I have been in contact with the FAIRmat team also about an error I had encountered upon uploading Yambo GW data. It has been clarified that the error was due to the NOMAD Yambo parser not considering the possibility of spin-polarized systems in the part which parses GW data. A. N. Ladines (FAIRmat team) has fixed this in the Yambo parser, and I have successfully tested the new parser version, which has then been included in the NOMAD platform.

Regarding the displaying of atom positions, simulation cell and chemical composition for Yambo files, I pointed out to the FAIRmat team the opportunity of explicitly indicating the need of having a ns.db file contained in a /SAVE subfolder in order to let NOMAD write and display the mentioned quantities. While making tests on this feature, I have discovered an issue in the parsing and writing of system coordinates by the NOMAD Yambo

parser, due to the use of the maximum number of atoms across all the chemical species present in the system instead of the actual number of atoms for each species, resulting in the mismatch between the reported total number of atoms and total number of atom coordinates. In collaboration with our internship student Hajar Belgroun, I have added a part of code in the Yambo parser, which addresses this subject, and made a Pull Request (including providing a test folder and the relative part of code) for its uptake into the NOMAD platform.

We are working (also in this case in contact with the FAIRmat team) on implementing the plotting of Yambo spectra, a feature that is still missing in the general NOMAD platform, and we expect to finish this implementation after the end of this thesis work. So far we have been able to implement the plotting of Yambo spectra locally by using our modified Yambo parser on Jupyterlab, but we are still encountering problems in running the corresponding parser on our Oasis.

For the Siesta parser, in collaboration with our postdoc colleague Masoumeh Alihosseini, we have successfully solved an error in the parsing of the type of exchange and correlation functional used, and we have implemented the plotting of electronic Density of States (DOS) outputs, although in this latter case the parsing of the Fermi energy (needed to set the zero of the energy axis in the DOS plot) is still missing, and moreover the parser does not recognize correctly the spin-polarized vs. unpolarized character of the system.

As possible future subjects to be addressed we can mention: completing our implementation of the plotting of Yambo spectra; implementing the plotting of Yambo GW-corrected band structures; completing our implementation of DOS plotting from Siesta by letting Yambo parse the Fermi energy and correctly identify spin-polarized vs. unpolarized systems, and, for the same code, implementing the plotting of band structures.

In addition to the work on the NOMAD parsers, I have also taken care of further data management and curation tasks within the UMIL Theo&Sim lab. I have installed an Oasis (i.e. a local instance of NOMAD) on my computer, which I have then extensively used for locally testing all the parser modifications discussed above, and I have assisted our IT team in installing an Oasis for the whole UMIL Theo&Sim lab, to be used for uploading our data in a structured and FAIR-compliant way, in view of eventually transferring them to the general NFFA-DI Oasis. I have organized specific NOMAD hands-on meetings focused on each of the NOMAD-supported codes most used in our lab - and I plan to organize further such meetings in the future - in order to instruct UMIL Theo&Sim researchers on the use of NOMAD for uploading computational materials science data. Finally, I have prepared the

Data Management Plans and the Interactive Remote Access forms for all the computational techniques offered by the UMIL Theo&Sim lab to external users through user calls.

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